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Гулямов Саидахроп Саидахмедович, Икрамов Мурат Акромович, Абдурашидова Нигора Алишеровна	
РОЛЬ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО ТРУДА В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЕГО ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ	6
Kucharov Abror Sobirjonovich, Bobojonov Azizjon Babaxanovich, Ishmanova Dinora Nurmamad qizi	
YOQILG‘I-ENERGETIKANI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA QUVUR TRANSPORTINI RIVOJLANTIRISH STRATEGIYASI	15
Axmedova Elnora Mamur qizi	
XUSUSIY TA‘LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINING RIVOJLANISHI VA ULARDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	22
Abdurashidova Nigora Alisherovna	
COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN'S AUTOMOBILE SECTOR: UTILIZING BENCHMARKING FOR ENHANCED COMPETITIVENESS.....	28
Xakimov Ziyodulla Axmadovich, Raximov Furqat Jalolovich	
TO‘QIMACHILIK MAHSULOTLARI RAQAMLI PASPORTINI YARATISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARI	35
Mannopova Manzura Jamil qizi	
XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDA NASHRIYOT SANOATIDA FOYDALANILADIGAN RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA ULARNING TASNIFI	52
Kadirova Umida Ergashevna	
JAHONDA VA O‘ZBEKISTONDA “XALQCHIL IPO”NING SHAKLLANISHI VA UNING RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI	59
Raxmonberdiyeva Feruza Rixsiboyevna, Bababekova Nargiza Baxtiyorovna	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT — RIVOJLANISHNING REAL OMILIDIR	70
Mannopova Manzura Jamil qizi	
NASHRIYOTDA ZAMONAVIY AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	79
Saidova Dilnozaxon Odiljon qizi	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA RAQOBATBARDOSH AFZALLIKLAR YARATISH VA SAQLAB QOLISHNING IJTIMOYIY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARI	86
Aslonova Rushano Ilxomovna	
MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA‘LIMI TIZIMIDA BILIMLAR IQTISODIYOTINI “GAMIFIKATSIYALASH”NING USLUBIY ASOSLARI.....	95
Samiyeva Maftuna Faxriddin qizi	
TASHKILOTLARDA AXBOROT TIZIMLARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH VA QO‘LLAB-QUVVATLASH JARAYONIDA AUTSORSINGNING ROLI	101

Usmonova Diyora Mahmud qizi UZUMCHILIK KORXONALARI BOZOR TADQIQOTI FAOLIYATIDA MIJOZLAR MA'LUMOTLARI TAHLILIGA ASOSLANGAN MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	106
Xo'jayev Fazliddin Elmurodovich O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA XALQARO YUK TASHUVLARINI TASHKIL ETISH VA BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	117
Masharipova Xosiyat Matrasulovna MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGIGA INVESTITSİYALAR TA'SIRINING EKONOMETRIK TADQIQI.....	126
Ikromov Axmadjon Shavkat o'g'li OZIYQ-OVQAT KORXONALARIDA MAHSULOT RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI BOSHQARISHNING IQTISODIY MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	133
Siddikov Nizomiddin G'ulomovich TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINING MAMLAKAT IQTISODIY-IJTIMOY RIVOJLANISHIDAGI O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI	140
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna, Zaripov Otabek Zaripovich LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA SUG'URTALASHNING O'RNI .	151
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna, Tuymayev Sardor Sanjar o'g'li TRANSPORT VA LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA SUG'URTA XIZMATLARINING AHAMIYATI.....	156
Samiyev Siroj Saitovich, Mustafaqulova Sitara Sho'hratovna TOURIST ARRIVALS IN ARGENTINA.....	161
Ruziyeva Shaxlo Raupovna RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI UCHUN TAHDID VA IMKONIYATLAR.....	168
Xasanov Soxib Latifovich FARMATSEVIKA FAOLIYATIDA BRENDINGDAN FOYDALANISH YO'NALISHLARI	175
Ulug'murodov Farxod Faxriddinovich, Ulasheva Sabina Adxam qizi YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI BAHOLASH INDIKATORLARINI ISHLAB CHIQUISHGA ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	181
Akbarov Nodir G'afurovich RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA FAN, TA'LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQUARISH INTEGRATSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI HAMDA ZAMONAVIY MODELLARI.....	186
Madrimov Shuhrat Bahodir o'g'li, Vahobov Anvar Abdumannop o'g'li KAPITAL BOZORINING JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA SHAXSIY INVESTITSIYA HISOBVARAG'INING O'RNI	193
Fayzullayev Jonibek Mambetsaliy o'g'li QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATI KORXONALARIDA ZAMONAVIY BOSHQARUV USULLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH STRATEGIYASI.....	200

Mamasoliev G‘ayratbek Maxamadyusupovich O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI TURIZM SOHASINI TRANSPORT XIZMATLARI BILAN TA‘MINLANISH.....	211
Turolov Maqsudjon Asatillo o‘g‘li ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ИНФОРМАЦИОННОГО МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЯ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ ЖИЛИЩНЫМ ФОНДОМ: СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТРЕНДЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ.....	219
Кахрамонов Хуршиджон Шухрат угли ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫЕ КЛАСТЕРЫ КАК ДРАЙВЕР МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ И ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ ЭКОНОМИКИ.....	228
Муминова Умидахон Дильшод кизи TURIZM SOHASINING INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISH OMILLARI.....	237
Fayazov Muxiddin Sobirovich О‘ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTINI TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYALASHUV JARAYONLARINI JADALLASHTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO‘NALISHLARI.....	246
Mallaboyev Anvarjon Sotvoldiyevich РАЗВИТИЕ АВТОМОБИЛЕСТРОЕНИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ И РАЗВИТИЕ, ПРОИСХОДЯЩИЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ.....	255
Абдухамидова Мафтуна Турсунали кизи OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATI KORXONALARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH SALOHİYATINI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	263
Shukurov Rustam Ergash o‘g‘li TIBBIY XIZMATLAR BOZORIDA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY OMILLARI TAHLILI.....	270
Vaisov Dilshod Ibodullayevich MARKAZIY OSIYO HAMDA ARAB DAVLATLARINING ENERGIYA ISHLAB CHIQRISH HAJMI VA UNING TARKIBI TAHLILI.....	281
Najmiddinov Yahyo Fazliddin o‘g‘li ATROF-MUHITGA YO‘NALTIRILGAN BIZNES “YASHIL” IQTISODIYOTNING HARAKATLANTIRUVCHI KUCHI SIFATIDA.....	291
Isroilov Dilshodbek Rustamovich “YASHIL” IQTISODIYOTNI BAHOLASHDA INSON KAPITALI ROLI.....	299
O‘roqova Dilfuza Bahriddinovna AYLANMA MABLAG‘LAR AYLANUVCHANLIGINI TEZLASHTIRISHGA OMILLAR TA‘SIRINI BAHOLASH.....	305
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich AYLANMA MABLAG‘LAR AYLANUVCHANLIGINI TEZLASHTIRISHGA OMILLAR TA‘SIRINI BAHOLASH.....	314

TOURIST ARRIVALS IN ARGENTINA

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Abstract

Tourism is one of the developing spheres throughout the world. This survey displays the most essential factors that impact tourist arrivals in Argentina, focusing on data between 1995 and 2016 from three different countries: Bolivia, Brazil, and Chile. The research analyzed how having a common spoken language, tourist income in origin, distance between origin countries and Argentina, political stability in origin countries, and tourist income in distance affect tourism. To gain data, 5 independent variables were analyzed using linear regression in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program. As a result, the distance between origin countries and Argentina is the most significant key factor influencing tourism. Although factors such as having a common spoken language, tourist income in origin, political stability in origin, and tourist income in distance also play a medium role in shaping tourist flows. This research provides a comprehensive understanding of the drivers of international tourism to Argentina, offering valuable implications for policymakers and stakeholders.

Keywords: Tourist arrivals; Argentina tourism; Linear regression analysis; Key influencing factors

Аннотация

Туризм является одной из развивающихся сфер в мире. В этом исследовании показаны наиболее важные факторы, влияющие на прибытие туристов в Аргентину, с упором на данные за период с 1995 по 2016 год в трех разных странах: Боливии, Бразилии и Чили. В ходе исследования было проанализировано, как наличие общего разговорного языка, туристический доход по месту происхождения, расстояние между странами происхождения и Аргентиной, политическая стабильность по происхождению и туристический доход по месту происхождения влияют на туризм. Чтобы получить данные, 5 независимых переменных были проанализированы в программе Статистического пакета для социальных наук (SPSS) с использованием линейной регрессии. В результате расстояние между странами происхождения и Аргентиной является наиболее важным ключевым фактором, влияющим на

туризм. Хотя такие факторы, как наличие общего разговорного языка, туристический доход в стране происхождения, политическая стабильность в стране происхождения и доход от туризма на расстоянии, также играют среднюю роль в формировании туристических потоков. Эти исследования дают всестороннее понимание движущих сил международного туризма в Аргентину, предлагая ценные выводы для политиков и заинтересованных сторон.

Ключевые слова: Туристские прибытия; Аргентинский туризм; Линеинный регрессионный анализ; Ключевые факторы влияния.

Annotatsiya

Turizm butun dunyoda rivojlanayotgan sohalardan biridir. Ushbu so'rov Argentinaga sayyohlarning kelishiga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan eng muhim omillarni ko'rsatadi, 1995 va 2016- yillardagi uchta turli mamlakatlardagi ma'lumotlarga e'tibor qaratadi: Boliviya, Braziliya va Chili. Tadqiqotda umumiy og'zaki tilga ega bo'lish, kelib chiqishi bo'yicha sayyohlik daromadi, kelib chiqqan mamlakatlar va Argentina o'rtasidagi masofa, kelib chiqishi bo'yicha siyosiy barqarorlik va masofadagi turistik daromad tahlil qilindi. Ma'lumot olish uchun 5 ta mustaqil o'zgaruvchilar Ijtimoiy fanlar uchun Statistik paket (SPSS) dasturida chiziqli regressiya yordamida tahlil qilindi. Natijada, kelib chiqqan mamlakatlar va Argentina o'rtasidagi masofa turizmga ta'sir qiluvchi eng muhim omil hisoblanadi. Garchi umumiy og'zaki tilga ega bo'lish, turistik daromadning kelib chiqishi, siyosiy barqarorlik va masofadagi turistik daromad kabi omillar ham turistik oqimlarni shakllantirishda o'rtacha rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu tadqiqotlar Argentinaga xalqaro turizmning harakatlantiruvchi omillari haqida keng qamrovli tushuncha beradi va siyosatchilar va manfaatdor tomonlar uchun qimmatli natijalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Turistlarning kelishi; Argentina turizmi; Chiziqli regressiya tahlili; Asosiy ta'sir etuvchi omillar.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the most significantly increasing spheres throughout the world, contributing rapidly to economic expansion and cultural exchange. Understanding the elements affecting tourist arrivals in specific countries is crucial for promoting tourism plans or strategies and increasing its profits. Argentina is well-known for its rich cultural heritage, beautiful destinations, and historical and modern landscapes among tourists. This research aims to provide the most important factors influencing tourist arrivals in Argentina from 1995 to 2016 in three different countries: Brazil, Bolivia, and Chile. The study mainly focuses on elements such as having a common spoken language, tourist income in the origin country, distance between origin countries and Argentina, political stability in the origin country, and tourist income in distance.

Drawing on recent exploration and theoretical frameworks, McKercher (2021) findings display that distance is the most essential factor influencing the tourism sphere. This opinion is clearly tied to the idea that distance from the source increases. Moreover, findings from the last 20 years have illustrated that overall demand

decreases by approximately 50% for every 1,000 kilometers farther from the source market. The research also established that distance impacts which types of travelers are most likely to visit countries and their behavior with distance. For instance, youthful office employees with limited holiday time, families concerned about very high travel costs, and individuals traveling for enjoyment or relaxation are much more likely to choose countries that are closer to home.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE

Tourism has been widely recognized as a vital driver of economic growth across the globe. Researchers Meltiz and Toubal (2014) examine the role of linguistic factors in global trade; they argue that it is crucial for each country or region to have a native language to strengthen and preserve its culture. This is why researchers have studied the common languages, particularly official languages, spoken across 195 countries. These official and shared languages play a significant role in influencing linguistic factors and in enhancing the understanding of ethnic identities. The research highlights that linguistic factors, when considered as a whole, have a much greater impact on bilateral trade than what is typically indicated by just the presence of a common official language. Furthermore, ease of communication is found to have an independent effect on trade, separate from the influence of ethnicity and trust. Translation and interpreters, in particular, contribute significantly to improving communication. Additionally, the role of emigrants is shown to be important in shaping the influence of ethnicity and trust on linguistic relationships.

According to Awan et al. (2021), research on the impact of people's income levels can affect the tourism sphere. In particular, it suggests that the wealthiest individuals who earn more and those with lower salaries are less affected by income changes, while middle-income individuals are more sensitive to such changes. The research analyzes information from 1995 to 2016 across 192 countries and applies a gravity model to survey tourism flows. The study illustrates that income flexibility largely depends on a country's income level, which directly affects tourism. As a result, there is an inverted connection: middle-income countries are more responsive to changes related to money or salary, while low- and high-income countries are less responsive to such changes. Lastly, high-income countries display either weak or no relationship.

The next researchers, Khalid et al. (2022), used a gravity model to analyze how different languages can influence international tourism. These elements are calculated using a widespread language index, which considers native linguistic similarity. The research illustrates that linguistic communication can significantly promote international tourist flows. This positive impact is not limited to countries with a shared official or non-official language but is also widespread to those with similar languages, minority categories linked by a common language, or languages that are closely connected.

The authors, Okafor et al. (2022), studied how the role of language can impact migration figures and international tourism. For the research, the authors analyzed 166

origin countries and 30 destination countries from 1995 to 2010. The study illustrates that higher migration rates boost tourism flows to destination areas. Moreover, tourist arrivals are minimally influenced when countries share closer or the same linguistic ties. The results show that, after COVID-19, governments aim to attract skilled foreign employees and international students who can expand linguistic networks and increase multilingualism. Closer linguistic ties can, in turn, enhance international tourist flows.

Cicowicz et al. (2024) analyzed the effects of COVID-19, which began spreading at the start of 2020. Many countries were severely impacted by the virus, which significantly affected political stability and tourism flows. As the virus spread worldwide, the authors examined a tourism program implemented in Argentina, analyzing its impacts on the tourism sector and the broader economy. The researchers found that strong political stability in origin countries can help boost the tourism industry.

METHODOLOGY

The primary data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to analyze tourist arrivals in Argentina with "Linear regression." Data were collected from the official website of the World Bank, which provides detailed information on yearly tourist arrivals from three different countries: Bolivia, Brazil, and Chile. The dependent variable in the analysis is tourist arrivals, while independent variables may include factors such as having a common spoken language, tourist income in the origin country, distance between origin countries and Argentina, political stability in the origin country, and tourist income in distance. By combining these factors, the study can cover important elements that influence tourist arrivals in Argentina. Organizational records and written resources were used as secondary data.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

Tourist arrivals in Argentina (Intou) = β + α col + α_1 touristIncome_orig + α_2 distance + α_3 pl_orig + α_4 touristIncome_dest + ε

Intou- is dependent variable;

α , α_1 α_6 --- are the coefficient of the independent variables;

ε – error term.

β – constant.

Result

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.972 ^a	.945	.939	.200174083084320

a. Predictors: (Constant), touristincome_dest, distance, touristincome_orig, pl_orig, col

Coefficientsa

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-35.352	11.041		-3.202	.002
	col	1.899	.934	1.112	2.033	.047
	touristincome_orig	1.403	.359	1.469	3.909	<.001
	distance	2.895	1.346	1.084	2.150	.036
	pl_orig	.391	.116	.227	3.375	<.001
	touristincome_dest	1.462	.386	.248	3.784	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Intou

The table displays parameter estimates from a statistical model with the help of ordinal logistic regression. To begin with, R squared shows 0.97, meaning that tourist arrivals in Argentina have been explained by the independent variable by 97%.

Firstly, having a common spoken language between the origin and Argentina is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. We accept H_a and reject H_0 , meaning that there is a positive relationship between having a common spoken language between the origin and destination and tourist arrivals in Argentina. If Argentina has a common spoken language with origin countries, it leads to an increase in tourist arrivals in Argentina by 1.8%. Having a common spoken language between origin countries and Argentina significantly increases tourist arrivals for several reasons. It makes communication easier, helping tourists feel more comfortable and confident during their travel. A shared language also builds cultural familiarity, encouraging people to choose Argentina as a destination. It allows Argentina to market itself more effectively to tourists and attract visitors from business or family connections.

Next, the tourist income in the origin is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. We accept H_a and reject H_0 , meaning that there is a positive relationship between tourist income in the origin and tourist arrivals in Argentina. If there is a one percent increase in tourist income in the origin, it leads to an increase in tourist arrivals in Argentina by 1.4%. Tourist income in the origin country significantly influences tourist arrivals in Argentina. One reason for this is that higher tourist income reflects greater disposable income among the population, which increases the likelihood of people traveling abroad, including to Argentina. When people have more money to spend, they are more likely to invest in international travel. Additionally, countries with higher tourism income tend to have better travel infrastructure, such as stronger transport connections and effective marketing.

However, the distance between the origin and Argentina is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. We accept H_a and reject H_0 , meaning that there is a positive relationship between distance and tourist arrivals in Argentina. If there is a one percent

increase in distance between the origin and Argentina, it leads to an increase in tourist arrivals in Argentina by 2.8%. The distance between origin countries and Argentina is positively associated with tourist arrivals due to several factors. Shorter distances decrease travel costs, including airfare and time spent on the road, making Argentina more accessible to tourists from close countries. Most tourists prefer closer destinations to reduce expenses and travel fatigue. Additionally, logistical advantages such as more direct flights or shorter travel durations can encourage visits. These factors collectively explain why decreased distance leads to an increase in tourist arrivals in Argentina.

Additionally, political stability in the origin is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. We accept H_a and reject H_0 , meaning that there is a positive relationship between political stability in the origin and tourist arrivals in Argentina. If political stability increases in origin countries, it leads to an increase in tourist arrivals in Argentina by 0.3%. Political stability can increase tourist arrivals in Argentina because tourists feel personal safety and confidence during travel. In politically stable places, people are more likely to prioritize leisure, travel, and explore the city, which tourists cannot do in politically unstable countries.

Lastly, the tourist income in distance is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. We accept H_a and reject H_0 , meaning that there is a positive relationship between tourist income in both origin and destination countries and tourist arrivals in Argentina. If there is a one percent increase in tourist income in distance, it leads to an increase in tourist arrivals in Argentina by 1.4%. Tourist income in the distance significantly influences tourist arrivals in Argentina. The reason is that a higher income salary allows people to allocate more resources to optional spending, such as international travel. Due to this, people who live farther away can lead more luxurious lives and create or build more beautiful, attractive places for tourists, which definitely can influence tourist arrivals in Argentina.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

This research explores the main factors that impact tourist arrivals in Argentina between 1995 and 2016 from three different countries: Bolivia, Brazil, and Chile. Both primary and secondary data were used for the research. The primary data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program, applying "Linear Regression" to find the significance of variables in increasing tourist arrivals in Argentina. The research illustrates that the most vitally important factor for tourist flows is distance, compared to other elements. It was the predominant element in boosting tourist arrivals, particularly from nearby countries. The main reason is that distance can reduce the amount of time tourists spend on roads, helping them save more money. That is why distance plays an essential role in promoting tourist arrivals from one place to another.

The second most essential variable is having a common language between the origin and destination, because if tourists understand the language of the destination, it can help them travel without a tour guide. Additionally, tourists can find their way

more easily. On the other hand, having a common language helps tourists feel more comfortable than in places where the language is non-native.

In addition, tourist income in the origin country, political stability in the origin country, and tourist income in the destination country also play a moderate role in improving tourism in Argentina. International tourists visiting Argentina are more concerned about the distance rather than the price of airline tickets or petrol in the destination.

Policymakers should encourage airline companies to create affordable flight prices for international tourists traveling from long-haul origin countries. This would greatly improve the tourism sector in Argentina if managers and tour companies reduce prices for travelers from long-distance countries. Additionally, policymakers should focus on cross-border tourism with more affordable prices for citizens of neighboring countries.

Moreover, while political stability plays a moderate role, the government should prioritize ensuring safety and fostering a welcoming environment for tourists. By implementing these policies, Argentina can expand its tourism sector by maximizing key elements, attracting tourists from long-haul destinations, and benefiting the economy of the country.

REFERENCES

1. McKercher, B. (2021). The impact of distance on tourism: A tourism geography law. In *Tourism Spaces* (pp. 137-141). Routledge.
2. Melitz, J., & Toubal, F. (2014). Native language, spoken language, translation, and trade. *Journal of International Economics*, 93(2), 351-363.
3. Waqas-Awan, A., Rosselló-Nadal, J., & Santana-Gallego, M. (2021). New insights into the role of personal income on international tourism. *Journal of Travel Research*, 60(4), 799-809.
4. Khalid, U., Okafor, L. E., & Sanusi, O. I. (2022). Exploring diverse sources of linguistic influence on international tourism flows. *Journal of Travel Research*, 61(3), 696-714.
5. Okafor, L. E., Khalid, U., & Burzynska, K. (2022). The effect of migration on international tourism flows: The role of linguistic networks and common languages. *Journal of Travel Research*, 61(4), 818-836.
6. Cicowicz, M., Porto, N., & Cerimelo, M. (2024). Short- and long-term effects of domestic tourism promotion in Argentina after COVID-19. *Tourism Economics*, 13548166241235423.
7. Musaeva, Sh.A. (2023). Marketing research. Textbook "STAR-SEL" LLC publishing and creative department. Samarkand.
8. Musaeva, Sh.A. (2022). Integrated marketing communication. Study guide "Maharat" publishing house. Samarkand.

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